

Cloud Computing

J.UCS Special Issue

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This issue contains four extended papers from the 11th International Conference on Information Integration and Web-based Applications & Services (iiWAS2009), which has been collocated with the 7th International Conference on Advances in Mobile Computing & Multimedia (MoMM2009), held in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia in December 2009.

Almost 200 papers were presented at these two conferences, out of which we have selected four papers for this special issue. The initial conference version of the papers has been substantially extended to include thorough discussions on related work and comprehensive performance evaluation.

A collaboration between J.UCS and the iiWAS conference series has started in 2008, when selected iiWAS/MoMM papers were featured in special issues in J.UCS. In this special issue, the four selected papers focus on “cloud computing”.

As general co-chairs and program co-chairs of iiWAS2009, as well as the guest editors of this J.UCS special issue, we would like to congratulate the authors of papers which appear in this issue for their achievements at the iiWAS2009 and their inclusion in this issue. We would also like to thank the PC members of the iiWAS2009 who conducted the initial reviewing process for the conference and the iiWAS2009 award co-chairs for selecting the best papers.

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Guest editors
March 2011